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An intersectional reading of climate policy in Malmö, Sweden.

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Abstract

This thesis presents a critical policy analysis of the inclusion/exclusion of social factors and questions of equity in climate policy in Malmö municipality by using intersectional theory. The objective of the paper is to 1) investigate how climate policymakers view social factors and questions of (in)equity and 2) explore how social justice can further be incorporated in policymaking through an intersectional framework. Researching how people/institutions understand multifaceted social aspects, how they believe themselves to operationalize it and what they really do, is surely complex. Not only is it complex, but an intersectional analysis requires attention to contextuality. This project therefore led to a qualitative mixed-method which looks at the organization, the key documents and asks the government officials how they view the issue. The results showed that there is a strong inclusive ambition expressed in both policy documents and interviews. Simultaneously, some obstacles exist when including social factors relevant to climate. The findings can be divided into three categories: Organizational, conceptual (framing) and inclusive obstacles. An intersectional lens reveals that in the same manner as environmental issues have been deprioritized over other issues, such as economy and development - Social aspects have gotten deprioritized over ecological or technical. Institutional structures, processes, framing of issues and in extension policy responses follow a historical trajectory of prioritizing/deprioritizing certain issues. Even if individual government officials are trying to create change, more extensive structural changes are needed to truly move away from the historical path.

key terms: climate policy, intersectionality, institutionalism

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Preface

I am very grateful to all the respondents from Malmö municipality for making it possible to carry through this thesis. It has been incredibly insightful and rewarding to get such a good insight into the climate-related work in the city. This thesis would not have been possible without government officials, project leaders, and politicians who volunteered to be interviewed. In addition to solid material for the essay, you have contributed interesting thoughts and conversations about climate change and social inclusion. I understand that taking time out of your busy schedules wasn't easy, and I am very grateful for that.

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Table of contents

1. Introduction	4
1.2. Aim and research question(s)	6
1.3. Delimitation / Scope	6
2. Background	7
3. Theory	8
3.1. Previous Research	8
3.2. Theoretical framework and key concepts	10
3.2.1 Intersectionality	10
3.2.2 Operationalizing intersectionality (The institutional context of policy-making)	14
3.2.2.1 Feminist Institutionalism	15
3.2.2.2 Institutional rationalism	16
2.3. Relevance to Global Studies	18
4. Method and material	18
4.1. Method and material	19
4.1.1. Text analysis (Policy document analysis)	20
4.1.2. Interview guide	22
4.1.3. initial group discussion	22
4.1.4. Semi-structured interviews	23
4.1.4.2 Selection of respondents	24
4.1.6. Limitations	25
4.1.7 Positionality	25
4.2 Ethical consideration	27
5. Results & Analysis	27
5.1 Why organization matters	28
5.1.1 Siloes	28
5.1.2. External projects	32
5.2. Framing of climate issues	34
5.2.2 Anthropocentric worldview	38
5.3. Institutional processes of reaching out and inclusion	39
6. Ways forward	43
7. Conclusion	44
8. Bibliography	45
9. Appendix	50
9.1. Interview invite	50
9.2. Interview guide	51

1. Introduction

Cities are becoming increasingly important sites when it comes to climate change. Modern cities are characterized by an accelerating concentration of economic activity and people but also by a concentration of greenhouse gas emissions. At the same time, cities are also becoming increasingly important in the mitigation of climate change (Lenhart et al., 2014). As climate issues have gotten higher on the agenda, an increasing number of cities around the world have attempted to take advantage of sustainable development strategies, not only to create a greener city but also as a means to create a positive image in order to attract business and investment (Anderberg & Clark, 2013). A city that has been both highly praised and highly criticized when it comes to sustainable development is Malmö in Sweden. The literature on Malmö puts emphasis on the economic aspect of environmental policy management: where sustainability becomes the means of growth (Holgersen & Malm 2015, Stripple & Bulkeley 2021), or as a form of branding to appeal to investment (Anderberg & Clark, 2013). However, the existing literature is missing a broader analysis of the power dimensions of climate change policy. Is this only a question of class and economic gains? Poverty and economic inequality are deeply embedded in the social, political, and cultural structures that make up the society we live in. According to research, there are significant differences in the population's levels of political engagement, emissions, and sensitivity to climate effects. These differences in populations are affected by intersectional criteria such as gender, ethnicity, class, age, and geography (Magnusdottir & Kronsell, 2021). Thus, issues surrounding the climate are intricately linked with dimensions of power. Failing to analyze the climate issue from multiple perspectives could jeopardize the understanding of the issue and even further perpetuate inequalities. Using an intersectional lens will give a broader understanding of the climate issue and the context in which it exists (social, political, and cultural structures) and will aid in creating a socially just climate transition.

I propose that special attention should be paid to climate institutions. Climate institutions in wealthy industrialized nations create policies and directives that frequently become the standard for other nations who subsequently adopt them. Further, institutions produce power relations by fostering specific norms and values and by only including particular types of knowledge, for example, promoting technical or expert knowledge (Magnusdottir & Kronsell, 2021). Therefore,

this thesis will investigate the inclusion of social factors and questions of equity in climate policy and goals in Malmö using intersectional theory. Applying an intersectional lens to the reading of Malmö will create a deeper understanding of the city's development as a sustainable city and how it is interconnected with other issues in the city. A broader understanding of the complicated social, economic, and environmental effects that climate-related activities have on different social groups is needed. Climate-related policies need to be developed with social factors and questions of equity in consideration. Otherwise, there is not only a risk of policies becoming undemocratic but also ineffective (Laestadius, 2018). However, climate institutions still have a focus on economic and technical strategies as the main solutions for combating climate change (Magnusdottir and Kronsell 2015). Past research on climate institutions in the Global North has revealed a lack of understanding of socioeconomic differences and (in)equity among policymakers, such as the heterogeneity of the public with its varying needs and behaviors. This presents itself in how social variables relevant to the climate are incorporated into climate goals (Magnusdottir and Kronsell, 2015, Singleton & Magnusdottir, 2021). Global, national, and local climate goals need significant changes across all sectors of society. At various levels, governing institutions play an important role in this undertaking. Yet, these governing organizations have frequently failed to recognize that climate change challenges are social issues and require more than economic or technical solutions. The fundamental causes of climate change, as well as proposed policies and responses, are all intertwined in unequal power structures. Sustainable change demands a reorganization of societal relationships. As a result, in order to address climate change, we must simultaneously address questions of justice, equity, and power (Kronsell et al., 2021). A second issue in the existing literature on Malmö's climate policy is the time perspective; the majority of research conducted on Malmö's climate policy is from the early 2000's until the mid 2010's, missing half a decade of climate work that needs to be taken into account. Has Malmö responded to the heavy criticism by working to integrate sustainability into the whole city? Or is the state of development the same?

With the use of intersectionality theory as the main theoretical framework, this thesis departs from a document review, which works as the foundation for an interview study. The analysis of four documents, one initial group discussion (with four government officials and four researchers, including myself), and six individual interviews provides the research material that is analyzed to study the understanding and inclusion/exclusion of social factors and questions of

equity in climate policy as well as to capture proposals for improvement. The thesis is structured as follows: In the next sections, the research questions and the aim of the thesis are presented. Followed by a short background on climate policy in Malmö. Thereafter, the guiding theoretical framework and its relevance to the case are discussed. After that, the materials and methods employed are presented. Lastly, the collected data is analyzed and presented with the help of the theoretical framework.

1.2. Aim and research question(s)

The objective is to discover and address how climate policies and climate goals include and how policymakers manage social factors and questions of (in)equity in their work. To that end, the thesis applies an intersectional policy analysis and shows how it can be executed by combining document analysis, group discussion, and semi-structured in-depth interview studies. The objectives of using intersectional policy analysis are 1) to investigate how climate policymakers view social factors and questions of (in)equity and 2) to explore how social justice can further be incorporated into policy-making through an intersectional framework.

The research questions that will be used to conduct this study are the following:

1. *How can intersectional theory be used in policy analysis?*
2. *How does Malmö municipality view and manage questions of (in)equity in their climate work?*
 - *How are social factors relevant to climate and questions of (in)equity discussed in key regulatory documents?*
 - *How do policymakers experience that social factors relevant to climate and questions of (in)equity are handled?*

1.3. Delimitation / Scope

The thesis will focus on one single case, the case of Malmö municipality's climate institutions. Climate-related issues are dealt with in many different institutions by a variety of actors. Due to the scope of this paper a further delimitation was done by focusing on investigating climate

institutions in the municipality of Malmö, mainly the Environmental Department. The study will further be delimited by the time scale. Most earlier studies of Malmö were done in the early 2000's and 2010's. Therefore, this paper will focus on the current state and development.

2. Background

This section aims to explain the development of climate policy and goals in Malmö, as well as its merits and critiques. Malmö has a history of being a proud industrial city. But the once thriving city experienced a substantial decline in the 1980s and 90s, leading to the collapse of its industry (Lenhart et al., 2014). It was during this all-time low that Malmö started to work on its revision to become a 'sustainable city' (Holgerson & Malm, 2015). Stripple & Bulkeley (2019) point out how the creation of spectacular projects, such as the Western Harbor, has become a prominent sustainable planning strategy for the city as well as a means in an urban competition to draw international attention. Considerations of the environment became meaningful not only for sustainability, health, and general life quality but also to increase the attractiveness and growth of the area, which became an important component in getting the city out of the 1990's crisis. Since then, Malmö has become somewhat of a 'green' success story. The city has built a reputation internationally for its development towards a low-carbon city and has a long list of prizes and awards to its name. However, the revisioning of Malmö has been heavily criticized as a neoliberal economic strategy mainly designed for the wealthier parts of the urban population (Baeten, 2011). The economically deprived areas of Malmö have seen much less of the effects of this strategy. As the city is getting increasingly segregated, the image of a 'green city' is being challenged by the less harmonious social realities (Holgerson, 2012). The spatiality of 'green' Malmö is not coherent or homogenous. The 'low carbon' features of the city do not replace the 'high carbon', but rather coexist in a somewhat uneasy manner in order to preserve state and economic interests (Bulkeley & Stripple, 2021). This thesis builds on previous research in the sense that it takes a critical stance towards the eco-modernist logic behind the development of 'green' Malmö. As presented, there are a variety of studies on climate issues and sustainable development in Malmö. In the coming section, I will go further into the previous research on climate policy in Malmö and discuss where there is a gap in the research on Malmö, which I will aim to fill.

3. Theory

This study belongs in the field of environmental social science because it is social factors and processes related to climate issues that are examined, mapped and analyzed. Previous research thus consists of studies centered on climate policy and goals. The main theoretical framework of this thesis is intersectionality theory. To answer the specific research questions, the theoretical background is focused specifically on intersectional theory in a policy context. During the interview studies, other theories arose as well. The main theoretical framework, complemented with theories on the policy context, will have great explanatory potential to illuminate what is left unproblematic in the climate policies in Malmö.

3.1. Previous Research

Anderberg and Clark (2013) label Malmö's environmental policy management as ecological modernization, characterized by an optimistic emphasis on the ability to combine growth and environmental goals in a win-win situation. This viewpoint emphasizes the importance of market actors (Anderberg & Clark, 2013; Stripple & Bulkeley, 2021). Lenhart et al. (2014) show how this is true in the case of Malmö, which has been heavily influenced by large stakeholders, especially energy corporations. For example, the opening of a natural gas CHP plant by the company E-ON in 2009 remarkably increased the city's per capita GHG emissions. Holgersen & Malm (2015) call this transition a 'green fix', a version of eco-modernism. But rather than growth and sustainability being compatible, sustainability becomes the means of growth. The logic is to attract capital, investment, and affluent citizens through the production of a green image, in which environmentally friendly practices are advertised as features of the city. Jönsson & Holgersen (2017) argue that Malmö is a prominent example of a planned-political success where sustainability has become a post-industrial pride. Anderberg & Clark (2013), in their study on eco-branding in the larger Øresund region (in which Malmö is located), conclude that this branding has made Malmö prominent in global sustainability. At the same time, it draws striking similarities with earlier efforts by the city to appeal to investment. When concluding the document analysis, I found that the presentation of priorities and goals from the municipality is frequent. Comprehensive documentation of specific activities and evaluations is also available. But such documents are both rarer and harder to find and get a hold of. e.g. The Comprehensive

Plan, which is a document on sustainable urban planning in different areas of Malmö. A summary of the document can be found online, but the whole document has to be ordered by post and takes approximately two months to arrive. It should be noted that this document was read but not included in the final analysis, partly for this reason. But mainly, it was not included because the analysis proved fruitful enough with the documents the government officials had pointed me to. However, this points in a similar direction as Holgersson (2017) and Anderberg & Clark (2013): that it is more about visioning and branding than actual activities. Bulkeley & Stripple (2021) discuss Malmö as a ‘climate smart’ city, where ‘climate’ refers to low carbon and sustainability, and ‘smart’ as a promise of development for the future of the city. In the case of climate smart Malmö, the environment becomes the means through which economic accumulation is created. They argue that this is not a strategic project with a definite goal but more a frangible process of ‘hegemonies in the making’—where the municipal objective to improve the city, as well as its perception of itself and the future, is somewhat improvised. It is not so much a green ‘fix’ as it is a continuous process of pursuing and upholding circulation.

Holgersen & Andreas Malm (2015) argue that there are deep-seated problems with this type of strategy in terms of ecological results, both in the case of Malmö and more generally. But this does not mean that everything that is colored green is merely a form of high-profile branding. Highly developed areas with solar panels and recycling systems shouldn't be discounted for, but rather they should be further developed in all areas of the city. It was stated already in 2014 in the city's Comprehensive Plan that sustainable development must include creating a city with good living conditions for all citizens (Malmö, 2014). Five years later, Stripple & Bulkeley (2019) stated that it still remains to be seen to what extent such inclusivity will happen. The short-term economic resurgence of the city has, according to Baeten (2011), tensions that will surely cause socio-economic issues. This form of modernization (through spectacular projects) will lead to short-term urban wealth and a socio-cultural renewal of the city, but will long-term further exacerbate environmental and social issues. Spectacular projects create spaces of concentration of wealth, which are disconnected from the growing social issues in Malmö. The city is home to a number of areas where deprivation is concentrated. The uneven distribution of development will feed tensions and lead to increased polarization and segregation (Baeten, 2011). Holgersen & Malm (2015) argue that this calls for a policy beyond the green fix and

conclude that a more fundamental restructuring of the city would need to focus on improving disadvantaged areas, which are in strong need of restoration. This would have an environmental component in greatly reducing energy consumption. However, subsidies for working-class areas will not bring the same kind of publicity as spectacular projects.

This paper builds on previous research in the sense that it takes a critical stance towards the eco-modernist logic behind the development of ‘green’ Malmö. As presented, there are a variety of studies on climate issues and sustainable development in Malmö. What they all have in common is a focus on economic measures alone. Surely, class and economy are an important component. But is it the only one? The climate transition in Malmö needs to be studied with a broader lens to not leave out any perspective and risk creating an oversimplified picture of the issue.

3.2. Theoretical framework and key concepts

key terms: intersectionality, matrix-thinking, complexity, subjectivity, context, feminist institutionalism

3.2.1 Intersectionality

In order to achieve a socially just climate transition, it's important to consider how some demographic groups are excessively affected by inequality due to underlying social systems. Intersectionality illustrates how social identities operate on several levels, resulting in various possibilities, challenges, and experiences for every individual. Oppressions are dependent on and influence each other. Therefore, it is impossible to limit oppression to just one aspect of an identity. Accordingly, failing to analyze climate issues from multiple perspectives could jeopardize the understanding of them and even further perpetuate inequalities (Kronsell et al., 2021). Therefore, this thesis will utilize intersectionality as the main theoretical framework. Intersectionality has been used in many fields and often at an individual or group level, but here it will be used in the policy-making context, and therefore it will also be used as a tool for critical policy analysis.

Intersectionality was founded by black female scholars who noted significant absences within feminist and other critical theories (Crenshaw, 1989). From initially being about including black women's voices in the feminist debate, it has come to include all signifiers of power and oppression. As a theoretical framework, intersectionality is useful in a number of ways as it positions us both epistemologically and ontologically. Firstly, intersectionality is a social theory of knowledge in the sense that it is based on the notion of knowledge as contextual. As people hold varying social positions, knowledge and legitimacy will necessarily also vary (Lutz et al., 2001). With this insight, intersectionality is an epistemological practice that can challenge hegemonic conceptions. In other words, this means questioning the social processes in which society communicates, evaluates, and legitimates knowledge claims (Kelly & Licona, 2017). This lens can help investigate uses of conventional knowledge as well as what is unspoken in it. Secondly, intersectionality is a relativistic ontological framework, meaning it views the world as made up of multiple versions of reality, which are shaped by context and where truth evolves and changes. In this sense, subjectivity is complex and multiple. Therefore, intersectionality pays attention to both privilege and oppression (Lutz et al., 2001).

The foundation of intersectional thought can be summarized in three points:

1. Gender, race, class, and similar signifiers of power and oppression are interrelated and mutually constructive.
2. Complex, interrelated societal inequities result from overlapping power interactions.
3. An individual's or a group's social location in the context of intersecting power structures forms their lived experiences.

Intersectionality takes on what is called a, 'matrix' logic, which challenges 'single-axis' thinking (Crenshaw, 1989). 'Single-axis' thinking means thinking about oppression as a singular identity. Not everyone has the same experiences, and such a logic misses that. Imagine yourself at an intersection of the streets: Gender, Class, Race, and so on, with traffic streaming in from all sides. The experiences of individuals standing at these crowded intersections are obscured when attention is focused on the most privileged members of a group (Morehead & Hennessy, 2017). A single-axis approach creates a logic of either/or instead of both/and. This is important in policy contexts where an either/or logic creates hierarchies where certain aspects or identities can be

prioritized over others. If issues are viewed in isolation, there is a risk of silencing certain voices. In this way, intersectionality will be used as a tool to critically analyze established ideas, normative political practices, and ingrained habits of thinking (Lutz et al., 2001).

Many of the earlier intersectional works have been critiqued for being overly anthropocentric and neglecting the connections between in human/nature power relations (Kronsell et al. 2021). In order to broaden the analysis and include nature as a source of analysis, the perspective on intersectionality and intersectional policy analysis presented in this essay is influenced by the so-called posthumanist approach in feminist theory. This approach criticizes the logic that nature is a mere backdrop for humans or a resource for technological advancement and economic productivity. As a result, posthumanist feminism has helped to advance the understanding of intersecting power inequalities by including other non-human actors (Birke, Bryld, & Lykke, 2004). With this theoretical lens, questions of equity are not separated from their social and physical context. Instead, social, economic, and environmental issues are viewed as systemic and closely connected. Thus, the focus of intersectionality shifts from a purely identity-based to a structural and systemic level (Godfrey and Torres 2016). Instead of looking at systems in isolation, such a viewpoint can offer a more holistic and thorough study. This perspective is critical of the entrenched dualisms that construct the world as a collection of oppositions, which is present in much of Western thought; human/nature, male/female, technical/social, etc. In contemporary times, such dualisms result in a perception of science and rationality as being superior, and develop and sustain human dominance over nature (along with 'othered' people) (Rask, 2022). Resulting in both a misguided understanding of human-nature relationships as well as unjust relationships: In regards to which groups are perceived as more vulnerable or affected and which groups have profited from earlier, unsustainable usage of resources by privileging/oppressing certain actors and types of knowledge (Kronsell et al. 2021, Kaijser & Kronsell, 2014). Therefore, an intersectional approach pays attention to the social location of knowers. In the case of this thesis, the knowers are climate institutions and the people they are made up of. These are government officials at different levels, mainly from the Environmental Department. Intersectional logic encourages us to take into consideration the broader circumstances of the creation and consumption of knowledge, to question seemingly apolitical methods and logics through 'both/and' thinking to explore underlying beliefs and assumptions.

Working from the premise that all knowers are embedded in power structures, it emphasizes how knowledge production and consumption are innately political. Credibility varies among and between knowers rather than being uniform (Lutz et al., 2001). In the case of climate policy, this could play out as certain types of knowledge are overlooked, especially those produced by marginalized groups. Posing questions about the process of knowledge production in government institutions can reveal what type of knowledge is privileged over others in the creation of climate policy and goals. Revealing knowledge claims that are seemingly unbiased and universal raises concerns about who has been heard, who is seen as a valid knower, what kinds of information has been acknowledged (documented, stored, and passed down through the generations), and finally, who has had control over the means and access to the resources of producing knowledge (access to education, publication, and more). Thus, marginalized groups often do not have an equal say in defining or constructing what is meaningful.

The objective of using intersectional policy analysis is to discover and address how climate policies and climate goals include and manage social factors and questions of (in)equity. Intersectionality can expose shortcomings and exclusionary characteristics of conventional policy-making approaches (Hankivsky & Cormier, 2011). It is a difficult undertaking to understand the intersections of multiple social factors as a foundation for policy. Policymakers confront a difficult task in designing policies to address the different social issues that specialized groups face, while at the same time upholding their commitment to govern society as a whole. There might be a lack of both time and resources to consider the consequences of the intersection of these social factors. Instead, the aim is often to isolate each 'distinctive' area of issue. However, such a method is incapable of fully capturing the intricacies and interconnectedness of complex issues, such as climate (Wilkinson, 2003). In the coming section, I will discuss how intersectional theory can be used in the context of policy analysis.

3.2.2 Operationalizing intersectionality (The institutional context of policy-making)

Intersectionality is not guaranteed to be a fail-safe strategy to accomplish a more inclusive view of knowledge or transformative effects (Lutz et al., 2011). It is also not a cumulative identity

formula (gender + class + race + sexuality and so on), as though these were separate, sequential variables (Harnois, 2005). Rather, intersectional theory analyzes how privilege and dominance operate on multiple levels simultaneously (structural, political, and epistemological) and within and across different categories of lived realities (such as gender, class, race, etc.). Doing intersectional work is not about putting on inclusion theatrics, where intersectionality is primarily used as a decorative element or a meaningless gesture. Intersectionality's complexity is flattened by symbolic applications, which overlook the interpretative and political obligations it contains (May, 2015). It is not enough to only study goals and documents that state what 'should' be done. An intersectional analysis means actively looking for ways to interpret well-established single-axis logics and making a continuous effort to achieve real societal justice through ontological, epistemological, and structural development. Therefore, it is important to be cautious of overly instrumental or depoliticized models that ignore context and political history (Spade 2013). Thus, an awareness of the political and social history of Malmö is important in the analysis of its climate policy.

Therefore, I propose the following formula in order to create an intersectional policy analysis. There are three things we need to pay attention to:

1. The context (the institutions, the history of the location)
2. The social location of knowers (the historical trajectory of institutions; see 3.2.2.1)
3. The process of knowledge production

The previous theoretical section on intersectionality addresses the importance of a holistic view and contextualization. This thesis uses intersectional theory as a framework for policy analysis, so the context is the climate institutions. This means that, in addition to the policies themselves, the structures in which decision-makers exist and policies are developed and implemented are important for the analysis. The structure of these institutions and how they are operated are important factors, which I will bring up in the results. The institutional context is a key aspect of this paper, and therefore, this thesis will also utilize logic from feminist institutionalism and institutional rationalism. The term 'climate institutions' can be used to refer to governing entities at various levels, including state and municipal governments as well as international and regional intergovernmental organizations. In this paper, institutions, based on institutionalist thought, also

include norms, regulations, and practices of the climate of institutions and the people that they are made up of.

3.2.2.1 Feminist Institutionalism

The focus of feminist institutionalism has been almost entirely on gender. However, as earlier stated, this thesis suggests that an intersectional understanding of social factors beyond gender alone is needed for an accurate analysis of climate policies. Feminist institutionalism argues that social inequality is organized within institutions through both formal and informal norms and procedures. People embedded in institutions act in response to previous institutional activities and feedback, which facilitates the development of a specific historical trajectory, or ‘path dependency’ (Goodsell, 2006). Power inequalities are ingrained and perpetuated over time in organizations as a result of these historical processes, which in turn direct or influence political activities (Pierson, 2004). Institutions often have certain ‘pattern-bound’ outcomes over time as a result of following particular rules and behavioral norms (Lowndes, 2020). Institutions become ‘sticky’ due to this path dependency and, as a result, options for improvement and change are constrained by prior decisions (Miller, 2020). Magnusdottir & Kronsell (2021) argue that, in line with this viewpoint, climate institutions have been shown to be path-dependent in their recognition of gender and other climate-relevant social factors. This is connected to how climate change was first presented as a highly technical, elite, masculinized, and scientific matter, in which the natural sciences defined the issue and, in that manner, reduced the relevance of social perspectives. Singleton and Magnusdottir (2021) have, in their study, found that in the global North, climate policy and goals have mainly been managed in the environmental, transportation, and energy sectors. As a result, understandings of social power relations in policy-making will be influenced by the norms and cultures of the institutions in those sectors. In the context of this thesis, this implies that traditional economic and technological solutions are seen as more acceptable than those that focus on social aspects. Another form of path dependency that became visible in the interviews is the way that institutions are organized into ‘siloed’ structures, which in turn affects how climate issues are framed and dealt with—something that will be analyzed further in the results section.

Leading back to the question of knowledge and epistemology in intersectional theory, the path dependency of the specific climate institutions in extension affects the way that the issue is framed. The issue is identified within the framework of the specific institution. Accordingly, the problem definition (the climate problem) is influenced by those institutions. Feminist researchers have shown that how an issue is defined is important; for example, Carol Bacchi has shown that much of politics lies in the definition of the problem, and thus it is important to pose questions about the problem formulation or framing.

3.2.2.2 Institutional rationalism

The rationale of path dependencies in feminist institutionalism ties into a form of public policy tradition that Dryzek (2013) calls ‘Institutional rationalism’. As climate issues have historically been related to the natural sciences, they have become linked to a tradition of public policy that gives scientific expertise significant importance. Administrative rationalism can be defined as prioritizing the expert's role in social problem solving above that of the public and places more emphasis on hierarchical social relations than on equality. The aim is to organize technological and scientific expertise into a bureaucratic hierarchy in service of the state. In this rationale, a specific type of top-down planning can be found that centrally sets targets and specifies how to achieve them. Administrative rationalism assumes several hierarchies. The first hierarchy subordinates citizens to the state authority. The second establishes managers and specialists in dominating positions within the state's internal hierarchy, supported by expertise. Lastly, administrative rationalism makes the assumption that nature is hierarchically subordinated to human problem solving, thus taking on an anthropocentric worldview (Drizek, 2013). Using an intersectional lens can reveal such taken-for-granted logic and hierarchies.

The approach to problem solving in administrative rationalism is to divide into different subsets within the institution (in this case, departments). Here, interactions within departments should be robust, but interactions between different departments should be modest. However, such division becomes problematic when facing complex issues with a variety of elements and interactions across sectors. High levels of complexity mean that interactions will necessarily occur. No division, no matter how carefully planned out, can handle such complexity. Wapner (2002), in their study on

ecological displacement and transnational environmental justice, argues that in such an instance, the structure will lead to problem displacement rather than problem solving as the department structures prevent learning from being passed up the administrative hierarchy. Moving up the hierarchy, a lot of information is unavoidably lost due to the limited time and resources that individual government officials have to process information. Consequently, there is a dilemma for administrative rationality: the more disciplined an organization is, the less it will be able to learn (Torgerson & Paehlke, 2005). The more an organization learns (through building an open and decentralized structure), the more difficult it will become to keep up administrative standards of discipline, that is, hierarchical structures and expert management.

The basic components of administrative rationalism can be summarized as follows:

1. Recognized actors: the administrative state, experts, managers
2. Actors and their aim: experts and managers motivated by the interest of the public, which is defined in homogenous terms.
3. Assumptions about relationships: a hierarchical relationship where experts and managers control the state, citizens are subordinate to the state, and nature is subordinate to humans.

An intersectional policy analysis challenges these default hierarchies and departs from the notion that policy processes and the understandings that underpin them, such as expert knowledge, evidence, science, climate, and sustainability, are all values-driven by their very nature. Thus, knowledge is political. How the world is perceived, how social reality is produced, and, by extension, how climate issues are produced all have an impact on policy, practice, and outcomes (Bradshaw, 2019). A critical policy analysis has been carried out, which will be presented in the next chapter in order to understand how underlying beliefs and ideas impact the climate-related solutions that are adopted or neglected within the city's policy activity. But first, a discussion of this thesis's relevance to the field of Global Studies.

2.3. Relevance to Global Studies

The field of Global Studies can be defined by a few distinguishing features (Global Studies Consortium, 2008). The first characteristic is 'Transnationality'; which means a focus on global processes - rather than nation states alone. The study of a local case, Malmö, ties on to global issues of social (in)justice and climate change by looking at how these issues are experienced

and dealt with on the local level. Secondly, Global studies is an interdisciplinary field and uses a variety of disciplinary frameworks. It can include anthropology, history, economy, politics, religion, environment, social inequality studies and more. Using intersectional perspective makes it possible to incorporate multiple fields of thought by keeping the study process open and reflexive between findings and theory. Studying social injustices in a time characterized by increasingly shifting, hybrid identities calls for exchanges over the sometimes tightly policed disciplinary lines that often defines contemporary academia (Nash, 2009). Intersectional analysis starts at the multiplex of lived realities and approaches human experiences as complex rather than singular. Such works are challenging traditional disciplinary boundaries, as well as the compartmentalization and rigidity of ideas (Dill & Zambrana, 2009). Intersectionality is a contemporary narrative that was made possible by eliminating all kinds of such intellectual, but also political, barriers (Collins et al., 2021). This interdisciplinary tradition used in intersectional theory is due to the need to cross knowledge divides and makes connections across a variety of histories, identities and struggles. Critical interdisciplinarity is a way of questioning the ideological values, ontologies and epistemologies upheld by disciplinary norms (Maldonado-Torres, 2012). Which leads into the last characteristic of Global studies: The field takes a critical-theoretical as well as postcolonial stance to examine global issues, a stance shared with an intersectional lens.

4. Method and material

Methodologically, this essay is classified as a case study, which is operationalized through a mixed method of document analysis, a group discussion, and six qualitative semi-structured interviews. The case study is particularly well suited to producing in-depth concrete and context-dependent knowledge (Flyvbjerg, 2006). The method is defined as 'an intensive study of a single unit with an aim to generalize across a larger set of units' (Gerring, 2004). The case study has been criticized for precisely this reason: its generalizability. But even if knowledge cannot be formally generalized, critics tend to overlook the process of collective accumulation of knowledge. Generalizing is only one form of knowledge creation (Flyvbjerg, 2006). It should be pointed out that the study was not done for the purpose of being able to draw general conclusions about other departments or institutions. Nonetheless, from a larger scientific perspective, the

study can help to provide insights that can be fruitful in, for example, comparisons with other studies on the same topic. There is always a trade-off between depth and breath when it comes to the choice of design. On the one hand, multiple cases can allow for better comparison, but with a risk of overlooking context-specific knowledge (Bryman 2012). Climate change and the policy surrounding it is a complex issue consisting of multiple processes across multiple arenas and institutions. I have therefore chosen to conduct a single case study design in order to better understand the complexities of the case. The following chapter aims to further explain the methodological choices that have been made, as well as how selection, material collection, and analysis have been carried out.

4.1. Method and material

Intersectionality is often thought to be a difficult theory to apply (Hankivsky and Cormier, 2011) and has proven puzzling to policy-making and the professionals navigating the policy landscape (Christoffersen, 2021). Researching how people and institutions understand multifaceted social aspects, as well as how they believe themselves to operationalize them and what they really do, is surely complex. Not only is it complex, but doing an intersectional analysis requires attention to contextuality, or the context in which the issue exists. This project therefore led to a qualitative mixed-method study that looks at the organization, the key documents, and asks the government officials how they view the issue.

Method	Number
Document Analysis	2 Policy goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Klimatkontrakt, 2030, ● Miljöprogram för Malmö stad, 2021-2030 2 Policy reviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Voluntary local review 2021, A review of the city's steering towards the SDG's ● Miljöredovisning, 2020

Group discussion (online)	1 with total of 8 participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 4 government officials ● 4 researchers (including myself)
In-depth, demi-structured interviews (online)	6 in total, 3 of which also participated in the group discussion.

The methods used will be presented individually in the order that they were conducted in the following sub-chapters.

4.1.1. Text analysis (Policy document analysis)

The first step in this mixed methodology was to conduct a document analysis in order to become familiar with the climate institutions, goals, and policies in Malmö. This text analysis was carried out by a document overview and an in-depth analysis of the most relevant documents, where the findings will be presented in the analysis section.

There are a large number of regulatory documents that primarily, or partly, deal with climate issues in Malmö. To further determine which were the most central, the interviewees were asked which documents were the most important in their work. The two documents that were most frequently mentioned are *the Climate Contract (Klimatkontrakt Malmö)* and *the Environmental Program (Miljöprogrammet 2021-2030)*. The Climate Contract is a strategic document that sets the direction for the City of Malmö's long-term work on climate issues. The Environmental Program is a local declaration to work towards Agenda 2030. The program primarily focuses on the ecological dimension of sustainable development, but the social and economic aspects of sustainability are discussed as well. Two more documents were added to the analysis: *Voluntary local review 2021; A review of the city's steering towards the SDG's* and *the Environmental Evaluation (Miljöredovisning, 2020)*. These documents caught my interest because while documents of priorities and goals from the municipality are frequent, comprehensive documentation of specific activities or evaluations is rarer. In the plethora of documents available through the municipal website, these were the only two of their kind.

Firstly, I did an initial readthrough of the documents and familiarized myself with the texts. Secondly, I saved the documents as PDF files on my computer and created a color coding system with different colors for each relevant topic. The documents were read again more thoroughly and analyzed for recurring themes. How much each theme is talked about is important because it shows what is given space, i.e., importance in the documents. The information from the document analysis was further used to create topics for the interview guides.

This graph was used to present the findings from the document analysis in the initial group discussion.

Firstly, I read the documents and tried to identify any underlying intersectional logic in them. Such logic did exist, and one of the documents even directly mentions the benefits of intersectional thinking.

'Using intersectionality as an analytical tool broadens the understanding of the fact that people belong to multiple groups at the same time and thus may have different needs. Therefore, intersectionality can be used as a tool for creating custom initiatives and thus achieving the desired results. There is an ambition for gender equality analyzes to take on an intersectional perspective; that is to say, for them to shed light on how different power structures interact.' (Voluntary Report, 2021, p. 44).

However, the documents reveal other logic as well. Next, I compared the number of technical versus social solutions presented in the documents and found that technical solutions were more frequently mentioned. Furthermore, the texts sometimes expressed eco-modernist and anthropocentric logics, viewing nature and climate as a means for economic growth or as subordinated and a service to humans. I wanted to further investigate whether these underlying logics inhibit or facilitate how climate policymakers view social factors and questions of (in)equity. The most frequently occurring theme/keyword in the documents was collaboration (samverkan). It was highlighted as vital for sustainable progress and was therefore made into its own section in the interview guide.

4.1.2. Interview guide

Based on the document analysis and the research questions created with it, the interview guide was thematically divided into four categories (see appendix). The first theme aims to map out how climate issues are managed in the municipality of Malmö, as well as possible challenges or opportunities that might exist. For intersectional analysis, the context is important. This section aims to put the issue in its larger institutional context for a deeper understanding. The second set of questions aims to investigate the technical-oriented, anthropocentric, and ecomodernist logics revealed in the document analysis and how they affect how social factors relevant to climate are incorporated. Theme three focuses on inclusion (samverkan)—the most central concept in Malmö’s climate work, revealed in the document analysis. The last section targets knowledge and information, a concept central when conducting an intersectional analysis.

4.1.3. initial group discussion

In January of 2022, an initial group discussion was held via Zoom. During this meeting, four government officials presented their work on social factors related to climate. I got a chance to present my findings from the document analysis and discuss them with the government officials. This meeting served two purposes: Firstly, to familiarize myself and gain contacts for the later in-depth interview studies. Secondly, to get confirmation from the officials that the analysis of the regulatory documents was on the right track. Although this meeting has not formed part of the policy analysis per se (for example by providing quotes for the analysis), the meeting did

provide me with an introduction and a contextual understanding of the climate related work and the inclusion of social factors in Malmö Municipality, as well as examples of initiatives, themes, etc. that I could later ask further questions about in the individual interviews. Thus, influencing how and what questions I asked and, in that sense, likely enriched the results presented in this thesis. Additionally, the group discussion captured the experiences and opinions of more respondents and provided broader material than if only individual interviews had been conducted. Gustafsson (2014), in their book on qualitative research methods, explains how group dynamics can help respondents express and put into words how they experience different phenomena. On the other hand, group dynamics may have the opposite effect. Underlying power structures can affect who speaks the most or the inclination to bring up more sensitive topics. Thus, the method is complemented with individual semi-structured interviews, which in addition, will provide more depth on the issue.

4.1.4. Semi-structured interviews

The in-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted with government officials from relevant climate institutions. This form of interview is helpful in creating a detailed and careful examination of a specific case (Bryman, 2012). The interviews were then transcribed into written texts. The next step was to analyze the text, which was done thematically. Through this type of content analysis, the data was gathered under the set of themes from the interview guide. Each section from the interviews was then placed in a document together and analyzed again. Reading the respondents' answers side by side helped to further identify and study patterns in the transcribed data in the pursuit of answers to the research questions. The different themes and links between them became visible and were especially helpful when dealing with such complex concepts as climate issues and intersectionality. Here it is of most importance to be aware of one's own selection bias, which is always a risk. The way to reduce the risk of this is to do as open a reading of the data as possible. This includes paying attention to and mentioning outliers. Due to the qualitative nature of this study, no statistical analysis will be conducted on the data from the individual analysis.

The aim of this method of analysis is to find connections in the results and explain them with the help of the theoretical framework. The effort is to let the respondents give a picture of their

reality. The interview responses, divided into the four categories from the interview guide, have been coded into short units in the categories: Mapping, Challenges and difficulties, and Suggestions for solutions, measures, and wishes. The various problems are presented in the analysis in separate chapters and end with a joint chapter on ways forward, followed by a conclusion of both method and results.

4.1.4.2 Selection of respondents

Unlike in quantitative studies, where the selection process can be done at random in order to obtain the largest possible representation, the selection of respondents in a qualitative study should be done in a more structured way (Larsson, 2000). In this study, a sampling plan was created at the beginning of the project, where the research questions determined what type of interviewees would be the most suitable to provide data. For this study, those were government officials at different levels from relevant climate institutions in Malmö. Some of the government officials chosen for the interviews worked on the implementation of the Environmental Program. They were chosen so I could specifically ask about the document. The first step of finding relevant participants was contacting Malmö municipality to direct me through the relevant channels.

The selection of participants was complemented with so-called ‘snowball samples’, where participants were asked to suggest people they know or work with (Bryman, 2004). New participants were contacted until a saturation point was reached and no new people were suggested. This method is useful to get increased access to participants. One risk with snowball sampling is that it can easily skew to one sort of group or demographic, as respondents are likely to recommend people similar to themselves (Tracy, 2013). Since I am studying a specific phenomenon in a specific context, this should not be a major issue. Rather, it could be helpful in creating a deep understanding of the inclusion of social aspects in the climate policy in Malmö municipality.

4.1.6. Limitations

The original plan for the methodology of this thesis was interviews complemented by a ‘Mobile lab’ as a part of the FORMAS-financed research project Intersectionality and climate change

policy. A mobile lab is a set of interactive group interviews and study visit(s), in order to study a particular phenomenon in its urban context. It is advantageous because it creates a collaborative process of performing on-site analysis by an interdisciplinary group of researchers. This methodology creates a platform for co-production of knowledge with a variety of stakeholders (Palgan et al. 2019). In such a method, presence is central: visiting the place, the policy environment—something that was not possible. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the mobile lab had to be postponed until after the thesis period. Instead, a shorter group meeting/discussion was held online. This gave me a chance to present my document analysis—something that would not have been possible if things had gone according to plan. For the same reason, the individual interviews were held online. The problem with this is that the informal talk that usually takes place around an interview or meeting goes lost (Bryman, 2012). In spite of these limitations, doing one group session online followed by more in-depth, one-on-one interviews proved fruitful enough to answer the posed research questions.

4.1.7 Positionality

The case study was conducted within an intersectional framework. This demands consideration of both context and positionality (Hancock, 2016). As a white woman, I will contextualize what has brought me to this issue in the light of positionality and with regard to debates on white appropriation of intersectionality from black feminism (see e.g. Jordan-Zachery, 2013; Lewis, 2013). I live in the Global North in a predominantly white country, Sweden. In such a setting, I undoubtedly have a racially privileged position. Yet for a long time, I was not aware of it. This is not to say I did not know that racism existed; rather, until I started studying it, I was unaware of how ingrained, normalized and systemic it was. At the same time, I am a woman. Even though the female subject is assumed to be white, she is also assumed to be heterosexual. As a queer woman, I have often found myself in a position where I have to set one part of my identity before the other. In this sense, I could relate to intersectionality on a personal level. However, as oppression is intertwined, gender and sexuality are intricately linked with other oppressions, such as race. My reading of gender and sexuality will necessarily be influenced by my whiteness. In the same way that my able body, my social class, and so on will have an impact. This might be obvious, but there is also a second part to this. The rejection of gender and sexual norms that I have created will also come from my whiteness—those acceptable to my construction of self. I

am more likely to accept and uphold white standards and customs and accept other white rejections of gender and sexual norms.

Why am I stating all this? Because this is to explain that even the most critical analysis of privilege one can make will still be affected by one's own positions. This is not to say that we cannot attempt to take on another viewpoint in order to learn how others construct and deconstruct the parts of their identity. One way to handle such an impossible situation (as we all necessarily take up a multiplex of social positions where privilege and oppression are intertwined) is to account for other sources of knowledge that question and reject hegemonic logic. This can be carried out both through the selection of literature and the selection of respondents for the interviews. Taking on an intersectional predisposition requires one to deliberately position themselves, as well as to expressly create interpretative tendencies, in a manner that challenges dominant logics, ontological traditions, and subjective processes. Both/and logics encourage us to develop and refine the ability to depart from dominant logics and to understand other lived realities, histories, and meanings. Simultaneously, it can help to understand structural differences between and within groups, as well as the influence of our various power positions in numerous and interrelated power systems (May, 2015). Intersectionality is meant to be applied in a contextual and reflexive way. Intersectionality gives tools for challenging default explanations and everyday logic that maintain and rationalize inequity as well as highlight discrepancies between declared objectives and actual practices (May, 2015).

This thesis will utilize a predominantly deductive approach by starting from this theoretical framework to guide the collection and analysis of data. However, it is important to point out that there are characteristics of inductiveness in this approach, as empirical data creates feedback on the existing theory from where the research project started (Bryman, 2012). An intersectional lens requires an openness towards the findings of empirical data, where different aspects come into play, not only the most obvious ones.

4.2 Ethical consideration

This thesis was conducted based on the research ethical principles according to the Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet, 2017). Firstly, the respondents should be informed of the

purpose and their role in the research and must thereafter agree to participate, but with the possibility to withdraw at any time. Secondly, data collected on respondents may not be used for purposes other than research and must be handled and stored in a secure manner. The information of the participants in this study is anonymized using a numbering system. It is not possible to identify any participants with the information given and therefore should not entail any ethical risks. In the first participation request (see Appendix), I explain the respondents' anonymity, that participation is voluntary throughout the process, and how the material will be used. The information was also repeated at the start of each interview to build trust that the material would be used correctly. The participants were also told when and how the result would be accessible to them.

5. Results & Analysis

During the interviews, I posed questions about the municipality's work with climate issues to get a better understanding of the context of the administrative work, what challenges the municipality is facing, and, in extension, how this inhibits or encourages the inclusion of social factors relevant to climate. Doing an intersectional analysis of Malmö municipality's climate work led to the conclusion that there is a strong inclusive ambition expressed in both policy documents and interviews. At the same time, there are some obstacles when trying to include social factors relevant to climate in municipal work. The findings can be divided into three categories: organizational, conceptual (framing) and inclusive obstacles. These three challenges will be presented and analyzed in the coming sub-sections, followed by a section on ways forward and lastly, a concluding chapter.

5.1 Why organization matters

It has become clear during the study that organization is an important aspect that comes into play in different ways. The interviewed government officials have identified problems and are trying to change the organization. Even if it does not directly affect social aspects, it is important because it makes it difficult for climate issues to come up on the agenda at all.

5.1.1 Siloes

Malmö city is built up of 14 municipal departments (förvaltningar), where each department has a specific area of work. The Environmental Department (Miljöförvaltningen) supervises and supports climate work in other municipal departments as well as amongst other non-governmental actors, such as organizations, businesses of varying sizes, and the major system owners in the city (Interview 1, 2, 6). However, since the work of the Environmental Department is strategic, it is not in power to govern over other departments (Interview 5), something we will return to further on.

Several of the government officials interviewed described the structure of the departments as 'downpipe'-shaped—a structure also referred to as 'organizational silos'. Organizational silos are defined as a distinct separation of employees, often by different departments with varying cultures, following the same approach to problem solving as administrative rationalism. Be that as it may, there is a general consensus among the interviewees that organizational silos are not optimal for working with environmental and climate issues, as the environmental work has more of an 'umbrella shape'—ranging across all departments municipality-wide and is based on the city's Environmental Program (Miljöprogrammet 2021–2030). At least, this is the case in theory—the practical implementation is less straightforward. One government official revealed that they feel that, in the eyes of the other departments, the work still falls heavily on the Environmental Department.

'I don't feel that it is common work for the city or a common priority issue so much.

I don't know if I'm harsh. That's my feeling anyway.' (Interview 6).

The difficulty expressed with trying to implement environmental work across siloed organizations is that each department has a focus concentrating on a certain type of development—where environmental work has lower priority. One government official explained that much of the environmental work today is about creating more sector integration and less of a siloed structure. But the siloed organizational culture in the municipal institutions creates challenges in integrating the work, and any organizational change will therefore take time and resources (Interview 5). Consequently, even though the process has started, it is still at an early stage. Another official explains that when changing a way of working or an organization as a

system there will always be resistance because people know their role and are comfortable in it (Interview 3).

Further, Noon & Heery (2017) have studied organizational silos and explain that the structure leads to what they call a 'silo mentality', where the work is concentrated on one function or area without much thought of how it might integrate with others. This mindset was evident during the interviews, as several participants (sometimes repeatedly) stated that they could only speak about their own department, sub-department, or role. One can argue that this is understandable—no single worker can be expected to know every role. While that is true, the pattern of it points to a lack of holistic perspective.

The organizational challenge expressed by the interviewees is a common and well-known phenomenon in environmental departments in welfare states. As pointed out in the literature, climate issues are administratively complex, ranging across multiple sectors and administrative divisions. Environmental issues cannot be entirely addressed by environmental agencies; instead, the sectors that drive and produce these issues must accept responsibility for environmental goals (Nilsson & Persson, 2017). As a result, successful climate policies require long-term efforts across multiple policy sectors—but where the focus might be on objectives other than climate mitigation (Matti et al., 2021). This phenomenon is referred to as Climate Policy Integration (CPI), which is related to the broader research field of Environmental Policy Integration (EPI). Literature defines CPI in various ways, but they all refer to the integration of a climate perspective into other non-climate policies (García Hernández & Lucatello, 2022). Examples of such efforts to move towards CPI became prevalent when some government officials spoke about their experience with the Municipal Environmental Program. For the first program (2009–2020), the Environmental Department created an action plan to be implemented by the other departments. It was unsuccessful, as several participants explained, because the Environmental Department does not have any mandate to govern over the other departments, only the city council does. Going through the channel of the city council proved to be a lengthy and time-consuming process where climate concerns were 'added' at the end of the process. Secondly, the other departments had a hard time seeing their role in the work (Interview 1), as it was too unspecific and did not create a feeling of ownership for the individual departments (Interview 3). In the end, many of the goals in the program were not reached (interview 6). As a

result, a new version of the program was developed in 2021, which is based on individual implementation by each department but with shared goals and visions. The new version is based on internal (between departments) and external (with non-governmental actors) collaboration to create common working procedures in order to combat the challenge of varying visions and goals. With the program based on Agenda 2030, there is a need to work more integrated, both with questions of equity and other thematic issues (Interview 2). Climate concerns are now set to be further integrated into the work in each specific sector. The program is still in its early stages of implementation (Interview 2,3), but the feeling around the new way of working seemed to be mostly positive. Be that as it may, one participant declared quite the opposite view. They expressed that many of the other departments still saw the Environmental Department as having the main responsibility for climate issues. The official continues to express that they do not feel that there's common work between the departments on a jointly prioritized issue (interview 6).

At the international level, a strong case for EPI was made by the World Commission on Environment and Development already in 1987. The report states that the interconnected character of contemporary challenges contrasts dramatically with the structure of today's institutions. Institutions are often independent, fragmented, and operate under relatively constrained directives with closed decision-making processes. Those in charge of environmental protection are institutionally separate from those managing the economy or other areas (Persson, 2004). Such fragmented structures became visible during the interviews. For example, the Environmental Department has no decision-making power over the land in Malmö, this belongs to the technical departments. As stated earlier, the Environmental Department does not have decision-making power over other departments either. Hence, not having any governing power over the land will certainly restrict how much impact the Environmental Department has on environmental and climate issues (Interview 5). On a national level, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) has advocated environmental policy integration for over 20 years. In a report from 1999, SEPA points out that integrating environmental, economic, and social aspects is possible at an overarching level. However, at the sector level, trade-offs or conflicts of interests are likely to arise where environmental and other societal objectives cannot be achieved simultaneously (Naturvårdsverket, 1999). Some conflicts of interest became noticeable in the interviewees' answers: One official explained that there are many challenges in the city, such as

more and better housing, decreased unemployment, increased school results, and much more. Thus, there is a lot of competition on what issues get prioritized (interview 5).

This phenomenon is also discussed by Hertin and Berkhout (2001) in their work on EPI at the EU level. They explain that the issue is the relationship between environmental and other sector policies, which is a zero-sum game. It is caused by the historically low status of environmental issues and a generally late engagement in sector policy-making. Combating climate change has been viewed as a question of lowering pollution and greenhouse gas emissions from the end of the pipe (Nanna, 2022). ‘Bargaining’ between issues becomes a way of addressing conflicts of interests. One government official explains that the Environmental Department is seldomly included early on in decision-making processes (Interview 6). Nonetheless, addressing climate issues in an integrated way will still be advantageous over isolated policy-making procedures. Nilssona & Persson (2003) argue that even if there are no pure 'win-win' situations, policy integration can still prevent blatant policy inconsistencies. Integrated policy-making provides more extensive and transparent overviews of policies and enables actors’ engagement in a more informed way (Hertin & Berkhout, 2003). In extension, this will help achieve equity goals in climate policy. If climate goals are not on the agenda and included in sectoral policy in the first place, there will certainly be challenges in broadening the analysis to include social aspects and questions of equity. A narrow view on climate related issues- as something to be solved by Environmental Departments alone - will challenge framing climate in an holistic, intersectional way.

5.1.2. External projects

Previous research has put Malmö under heavy criticism for its extravagant environmental projects as a form of branding for the city. Several participants expressed how the environment and climate have become an important part of Malmö’s identity, moving away from an industrial city to a ‘green city’. Since then, the climate work has gone from an extravagant project stage to a more regular daily activity (Interview 1,6). Projects of another kind are still a big part of the work in the Environmental Department. These are externally funded projects that have a large influence on what questions or issues are addressed. Who decides what projects should be taken on varies. If it is a larger project, such as an EU project application, it is considered if it

contributes to Malmö's work and fulfills any local goals, and decisions are made high up in the hierarchy. Smaller projects can be decided by individual project managers, but they still require connection to the local climate goals (Interview 5).

The positive aspect of externally financed projects is that there's a lot of space for testing new ways of working which are not possible in regular operations. The budget for the department increases, and it is possible to have more people working on sustainability issues. Further, the work can be developed with different methods, trying new arenas and reaching different groups (Interview 5), and it is possible to work closer to different needs (Interview 3). Different outcomes become visible and it is possible to adapt to the needs based on each type of process and the type of participation in that process. The advantage is that the way of working becomes less rigid (Interview 6). The negative aspect is the continuity: there are no long-term projects, there is a start and a finish date (Interview 5). After a project ends, there is no time for reflection or evaluation, and it is seldomly returned to (Interview 1). Therefore, knowledge and development might be lost in the process. One interviewee explains that climate related issues are being worked on, but because of this, it is done in an unstructured and very point-by-point way. There is an awareness that there is a lot more work to be done. The issue is not so much about a lack of knowledge: as personnel need to move from project to project, resources and/or competences are not always in the right place (Interview 1), leading to problem displacement rather than problem solving. When that end date comes, there is sometimes a wish to continue running something that was started in a project, but there is no funding to do so. It is problematic when something successful has been developed but it can not be continued solely because the project has ended (Interview 5). For example, the green student council, which one interviewee explained as a project that their colleagues continued to bring up as a great initiative, was not made permanent because the project financing had ended. With permanent funding, something more concrete with a mission and a structure around it can be developed. The current model misses this and if the projects want to be picked up again, it is almost like starting over. During the project, there was close contact with the involved schools. The green student council project was set up a few years ago and the likelihood of the same people still working at the schools is getting smaller with every year. The participants describe that the process becomes personal and it feels a bit frivolous. In other cities, permanent student councils have been developed. But the city of Malmö hasn't really done that because there is a will to work in different ways (Interview

6). Even if there are clear benefits of externally financed projects, there is a need for a system of methods. One official explains how they try to add it into the operational planning (Verksamhetsplaneringen). Individual government officials try to highlight when different perspectives exist, but there is a need for a larger structure on how to include different perspectives. For example, when making a chemical plan, there is a certain amount of support, or a structure, that is needed for how to bring in the perspective of children and young people (interview 3).

Further, other departments are not externally financed in the same way as the Environmental Department. They also work with projects, but not externally financed ones. One participant explains that other departments find these projects too complicated as they often include different systems and ways of working (Interview 5). This means that the departments work in different ways and have different organizational cultures. Different cultures within different departments can make it even more difficult to coordinate the climate work. Thus, common ways of viewing, managing, and framing issues are important. The next section of this thesis will look at how climate issues are framed and how they challenge the inclusion of social sustainability. Climate is seen as related to nature and the environment rather than social processes. When it is viewed as a social issue, it is mainly viewed in economic terms.

5.2. Framing of climate issues

During the document study of the municipal documents, it became apparent that the framing of the climate issue could act as an obstacle in creating inclusive climate policy. In the regulatory documents studied, it is stated that climate issues are understood not as isolated, but as overarching societal issues that are connected with other sustainability dimensions. Thus, climate initiatives are believed to lead to positive effects in other areas (Klimatkontrakt, 2021). Climate change is unequal in its effects on different groups. Vice versa, different groups have an unequal effect on the climate. The City of Malmö strives for climate work that does not create or deepen such injustices and believes that it is crucial for the city's development to reduce inequality gaps and improve the living conditions for everyone in the city (Klimatprogrammet, 2021). However, these goals are expressed on a rather superficial level and do not include any concrete approaches on how to actually achieve them—it is said what ‘should’ be done, but nothing about

how that can be made possible. For example, it is expressed that everyone should have equal opportunities to participate in climate work regardless of their economic status. At the same time, equity, gender equality, and anti-discrimination are addressed as important aspects of climate related work. In this way, it is highlighted that there are actually different conditions for participating. Using an intersectional lens on the documents reveals some aspects that are left unproblematic. The regulatory documents emphasize that economic inequalities exist in the city and that improving them is a prerequisite for climate work. The documents mention other social differences and inequalities as well, such as gender and young people. But it is not much more than mentioned, and the analysis is not broadened beyond economic measures. Social concerns are given only a very limited amount of attention. Citizens are mainly described as individuals or as consumers, and specific social categories are not taken into account. Generally, social groups are not differentiated between. For example, there is no further discussion or analysis of which groups are most affected by economic inequality and why—the population is most often defined in homogenous terms. Nor is there any analysis of how different groups are affected by the measures implemented in the city. Even though they state the importance of the social dimensions, they fail to concretely explain how they are included and worked with. The complex heterogeneity of the population is reduced to an economic measure.

To further explore what the regulatory document had left unproblematized, the interviewees were asked a number of questions. They were asked if and how social factors relevant to climate and questions of (in)equity are included in their work and what challenges come with it. Economic inequality was frequently brought up as a challenge amongst the interviewees in a similar way to in the regulatory documents. However, other aspects were brought up as well, such as gender, age, level of education, and linguistic skills. Malmö has a high level of immigration, and parts of the population do not have knowledge of the local language (Interview 5,3,6,2).

While there were some variances among some of the respondents, the interviews revealed a common notion of social justice. In general, the necessity for collaborative action was highlighted, both internally between different departments and externally with other actors and the population—something that will be returned to further on in the paper. What was noteworthy amongst the answers was a tendency to shift to an international perspective when talking about social justice. Malmö was talked about as a contributor to positive change and as an inspiration

for other actors (interview 4). A responsibility to understand how actions impact other parts of the world was emphasized, called a ‘consumption based perspective’. As Malmö has gone from an industrial to a post-industrial city, local emissions have decreased. But rather than disappearing, the emissions have been outsourced to other parts of the world. A consumption-based perspective takes into account not only the direct, local environmental impact, but also the indirect impacts on other parts of the world through local consumption (Interview 2, 3, 4). According to the literature, such a perspective strengthens justice and discourse and is essential to properly solve environmental issues and to bring attention to justice issues (See: Hult & Larsson, 2016; Rask, 2022). However, it appears that concerns about justice only apply outside of Sweden. Current social differences and (in)justices on a local level are mostly unconsidered.

One interviewee reported that there is a tradition of having an ecological/nature perspective on climate related issues, but there is a need for a broader socio-economic perspective (Interview 3). Other interviewees had similar connotations. Even if they did not explicitly mention such a perspective, many tended to talk about climate-related issues in terms of the environment or nature. Both in the documents and in the interview answers, there is a high emphasis on innovation and technology as the solution to the climate crisis, with the continuation of profits. It is continually stressed how important it is to move toward a world that is more resource-efficient. This is consistent with the course of ecological modernization criticized in previous literature. However, as is evident from the theoretical framework used, which views social, economic, and environmental problems and inequalities as intertwined issues, there is a need to emphasize the systemic nature of the issues and the need for broader sociocultural change beyond technical solutions and innovation alone. The aforementioned respondent continues by pointing out that in the past, they have not thought outside the box—there was a set ‘expert role’. They express that when working with climate issues, there has been a lack of looking beyond that role and understanding the issues' relationship to other issues. But this rigid expert role is starting to break down more and more. The expert role itself might not be breaking down. After all, one of the roles of the Environmental Department is to provide expertise (interview 2). But there is a growing understanding that there are many perspectives that need to be included at all times and therefore a need for a border analysis (Interview 3). One possible explanation for why there has been a lack of a broader socio-economic perspective and why it has not started to be

acknowledged until recently can be found in what several participants pointed out: The Environmental Department collaborated most closely with the technical departments, such as the city building office, the real estate and street office, and the service department (Interview 1, 6). One interviewee even points out that collaboration with technical departments has increased, while collaboration with social institutions, such as libraries or the Culture Department, has decreased (Interview 6). In a study on path dependencies in state agencies in Sweden, Singleton and Magnusdottir (2021) argue that technical agencies such as transport or energy follow norms, cultures, and rules that could make technological and economic solutions appear the most suitable. As a result, knowledge regarding the significance of social issues related to climate change might be disregarded. Even though the government officials are aware that there are social differences and that they are linked to the climate issue in various ways, it is again not much more than mentioned and there seems to be an incomplete understanding of the intersectional nature of climate issues and their effects. One of the government officials explains that there is a lack of context-specific knowledge of how social differences and climate is interlinked

'The problem is that we currently have very poor knowledge of exactly how climate and social differences are interlinked. We know that it is connected and there is a lot of research, so there is no question about that. But the concrete connection, the Malmö-specific connection, the individual connection. We have statistics on a certain development. But we do not really have a clear picture of the connection between them.' (interview 2).

In the end, interviewees frequently came back to thinking in purely economic terms, even when directly asked what other social factors exist. One official talks about influence and understanding, that is, who gets a place in the development of society. They explain;

'There is an array of arenas where the population has the opportunity to influence, but not everyone in society gets in there and that is the problem. Development projects tend to be technical and the majority of participants are white men. It is very clear who is participating and what voices are being heard. And that is about class differences in the end.' (Interview 3).

The interviewee mentions the overrepresentation of white men participating, showing an understanding of social injustice and unequal representation in climate processes. The respondent goes on to say that it is a question about class. One could argue that this sounds like a question of gender and race rather than class. This statement, on the one hand, points to an understanding of the importance of the inclusion of social factors in climate issues. But on the other hand, the statement shows a lack of attention to the multiplex nature of social factors in the framing of climate issues.

Another participant reflects on their time working in the Environmental department since the early 2000's. They explain how there used to be a big focus on ecological sustainability (as it was important for the city's identity to evolve from an industrial to a 'green' city). But they have seen a gradual shift from ecological sustainability to a larger focus on social sustainability.

'But it doesn't feel like there is the same commitment to Malmö being the best [Environmentally friendly city]. Although we are still one of the main ones. We were the best environmentally friendly municipality again this year. So there is still the fact that Malmö is a city of success. But we don't really have that story in general in the city. If you look at what other departments might think and prioritize [...] There I still get the impression that social issues weigh more heavily. The environment is also important, but it does not quite have the same weight as before.' (interview 6).

The quote tells us two things. First and foremost, it tells us how environmental issues have gotten deprioritized over time, rather than gaining momentum. But it tells us something more. A shift from ecological to social sustainability indirectly tells us that they are seen as separate from each other rather than together, as they are focused on individually. In this sense, portraying humans and nature as dualistic and employing either/or thinking instead of both/and. Including social aspects relevant to climate most certainly becomes difficult if they are not seen as interlink issues.

5.2.2 Anthropocentric worldview

As discussed in the theory section, institutional rationalism entails an anthropocentric world view and framing of climate issues, where the environment is seen as subordinated to humans. Nature

is viewed in this hierarchy as a resource for human appropriation or as an ecosystem service that has to be conserved (Rask, 2022). This world view became apparent both in the document analysis and in the interviews. The critical reading of the Environmental Program revealed that such a logic was apparent throughout the document. The climate and the environment are only perceived as scenery or as something without agency that must be protected from and by people for the benefit of mankind. The terminology employed in the documents describes nature as a resource for the city and its (human) residents, as well as something that offers gains, advantages, and ecosystem services. Anthropocentric framings became clear during the interviews as well. For example;

‘Just sustainable development cannot be limited to a number of measures [...] It is an interaction and a focused work first and foremost based on a human perspective’.
(Interview 2).

The climate should be saved first and foremost for the benefit of humans. Words like ‘ecosystem services’ and ‘green solutions’ were frequently used by the interviewed government officials. One talks about an ongoing project that aims to spread awareness of ‘nature-based solutions’. They explain that people do not understand the value and profits of green solutions, and they are developing a guide for property owners and residents (Interview 5). The environment and climate in the city are discussed in terms of human health, economic investment (Interview 1), improved living conditions for the (human) citizens such as cleaner air and cozy green spaces (Interview 4, 5), the value of the space in the city and how it is fairly divided, again between human citizens (Interview 3). The climate crisis has highlighted how closely humans are entwined with nature and the necessity of taking ecosystems and species other than humans into consideration. A posthumanist intersectional lens reveals an ontological issue: the dualist view separating humans and nature is untrue (Mansfield and Doyle, 2017). Therefore, a just climate transition would include placing the demands of the nonhuman world alongside those of humankind rather than below them. Instead of seeing nature as a service or backdrop for humanity, nature needs to be given agency and value in itself in order to create a truly just climate transition.

5.3. Institutional processes of reaching out and inclusion

Creating just climate policies that do not perpetuate existing inequalities includes making the institutional processes just. It is not only necessary to include intersectional aspects in the framing of climate policy, but also to create inclusive processes of knowledge production (as the knowledge produced is the foundation for policy). Participants explain that there is not one single model for knowledge production and that knowledge is created through a number of channels. Firstly, there are the more ‘official channels’, or evidence-based knowledge. This is from the political leadership, science, etc. (Interview 1,2,3,4). Secondly, there are qualitative (Interview 2) or ‘trust-based’ processes that are more open, co-creative learning processes. In such processes, not only industry, academia, and the municipality co-create knowledge, but it also includes an understanding that there are other actors in society as well who carry knowledge and understandings in different ways (Interview 3). This type of knowledge creation is carried out in a more practical or conversational way (Interview 2). Although mentioned, this second type of knowledge production was brought up by much fewer participants, which indicates that the first type of knowledge has been privileged over the second type in the creation of climate policy and goals. This raises questions about who has been heard and who is seen as a valid knower. An intersectional lens reveals that this type of qualitative knowledge creation is important because without involving different social groups in the process, there is a risk of overlooking certain perspectives or types of insights, especially those produced by marginalized groups (Lutz, et al., 2001). Additionally, these different ways of creating knowledge do not exist harmoniously side by side or have a system of what should be used when and where. One government official describes the process of finding new ways of working as ‘very schizophrenic’:

‘One second we should work based on trust and the next second we have very clear hierarchical structures in the organization. It is the same way with how we base our decisions or actions. We say it should be evidence-based and we produce a lot of desktop products (skrivbordsprodukter), but the next second we're out there and actually making things happen.’ (interview 3).

On the one hand, the participants talk about how there's now an increasing space for trust-based, qualitative, and inclusive knowledge production and policy-making. The new environmental program is described as a new start, a new way of working with internal co-creation between the departments. Working groups are under development with representatives from the various departments. The plan is to work together towards the goals in the environmental program and then apply to the whole of Malmö—not just the Environmental Department (Interview 5). Officials declare there is a break-down of the expert role. Previously, there has been an interpretive priority (tolkningsföreträde) of the public administrations—planners know how the city should be built, for example, then the citizens get to move in. From a lower position of power in this context, typically there is some form of negotiation, but that does not include communication, rather it is just two-way information. But now there is an increased understanding that the public administration should listen to the citizens rather than the other way around and actually co-create knowledge (Interview 3). The officials give examples of several inclusive initiatives and pedagogical networks that have been created. For example, a working group specifically targeted towards citizen involvement related to the new Environmental Program (interview 6) or climate ambassadors who operate in socio-economically vulnerable areas with environmental issues linked to their neighborhood (Interview 1). Thus, seemingly breaking away from historical path dependencies of administrative rationale. But on the other hand, the trend seems to simultaneously go in the opposite direction as the hierarchical structures persist. One government official explained that there are no proven and well-trying methods when it comes to inclusion work in climate issues except learning from past experience—stating that path dependency is a central part of the learning process.

'We haven't proven anything in this commitment work, except that we are, of course, leaning on previous experience.' (Interview 2).

Further, as stated before, one official expresses that they feel that there has been a shift away from cooperation with the Culture Department and other pedagogical institutions, towards increased collaboration with the technical departments (interview 6). Inclusion requires that the population have access to knowledge, where cultural and pedagogical institutions play a central role. In order to reach the goal of a sustainable city, every citizen must understand the issues at hand, but also understand why: 'what's in it for me'. Therefore, the municipality needs to be

better at informing people about the benefits of climate-friendly initiatives (Interview 5). A sustainable city also requires an understanding of people's participation, commitment, attitudes, behaviors, potential for change, and how to create involvement in something as complex as climate change (interview 2). Hence, learning for sustainable development is required. Unequal access to knowledge and information was a recurring issue mentioned by several respondents when discussing social factors relevant to climate. One official even describes it as a bigger obstacle than the economic aspects (Interview 5). A few participants explained that some groups are more difficult to reach than others (Interview 3, 5). It is clear that the groups that already have the most are the ones that receive the most (Interview 3). Many people who are in more vulnerable positions do not know how they can participate in or affect the climate work in their local area or the city as a whole. This can be seen in the unequal use of official channels in different areas. For example, the number of citizen initiatives or error reports is much higher in affluent areas, where the population has a higher level of education (Interview 5). A second interviewee brings up a similar point and uses an example of the organization Fritidsbanken, which works like a library for outdoor and sports equipment. Paradoxically, the groups that are financially vulnerable and would have the greatest benefit are also the groups that do not access the information and resources that the municipality makes available. Communication is brought up to be the solution, such as information campaigns both through traditional channels, such as libraries, but also more informal channels, such as different network groups or associations, etc. (Interview 4). Information is surely important. But in order to reach the population, it is necessary to understand the heterogeneity of the public. The Environmental Department is currently developing a communication tool, what they call a 'lifestyle-based dialogue tool', as a way of working much more focused with inclusion (interview 1, 2). It is based on simple questions that will shed more light on obstacles, opportunities, and even attitudes and motivation to better understand social factors in Malmö (Interview 2). Gaining knowledge about the citizens and the social differences in the city is a crucial first step to creating just and inclusive climate policy. In this way, the tool could be a productive way forward. However, the tool will be on a voluntary basis, which can be problematic. Vulnerable groups or groups without a clear position of power in society are more difficult to reach with information through the existing channels of communication. There is both less experience in having a dialogue with certain groups and it

takes longer time to reach them. Therefore, the data from the tool is likely to not reflect the population accurately, and seeing the population as homogenous will miss such an error.

The work has not come as far as to find a common way of working to meet the challenges of inclusion. The difficulty is that someone needs to coordinate this work. The Environmental Department has no direct contact area with the population and different social groups, only indirectly through the supervisory work of other departments. Most of the contact with the population of Malmö happens in other departments (Interview 1, 2). One government official explains that the Environmental Department's supervisory work of other departments is very pressured. Therefore, it is not possible to incorporate development work into the supervisory work. The current way of working with development of any type, including social inclusion, in the Environmental Department is to collaborate widely in the city through the already existing partnerships (Interview 2). Therefore, a new way of working where development work and evaluation are more integrated throughout all departments is needed in order to reach and include the Environmental Department in this work. One participant concludes that there is a central need for a bigger focus on working with strategic communication, not only externally but also internally within the organization, as well as strategic learning, where there is space to pause and reflect (interview 3). Which again brings us to the same conclusion—inclusion and integration of a broader perspective of climate related issues in all sectors is crucial.

6. Ways forward

Using an intersectional lens reveals that in the same manner as environmental issues have gotten deprioritized over other issues, such as the economy and development, social aspects have gotten deprioritized over ecological or technical ones. It comes down to an either/or logic of dualisms—environment/development, society/nature and so on. Institutional structures and processes, framing of issues, and, in extension, policy responses follow a historical trajectory of prioritizing/deprioritizing certain issues, which follows an anthropocentric and administrative rationale. Even if individual government officials are trying to create change away from this path dependency, more extensive structural changes are needed to truly move away from the historical

path. Further, similar ontological assumptions are revealed: siloed logic translates to 'single'-axis thinking. Complex climate policy needs true integration across multiple sectors, rather than 'added' at the end. Instead of adding climate objectives on top of other sector-specific policy processes, climate objectives need to be ingrained in the foundation of existing processes. One interviewee explains that just sustainable development can not be limited to a few administrative measures. Justice cannot be limited to removing unjust measures; rather the justice perspective must be implemented in all new measures as well (Interview 2). In a similar manner, intersectional 'matrix' thinking needs to be truly integrated into climate policy and goals (as well as other sectoral policies) in order to create just policy. This leads to the conclusion that the most suitable means to advance equity goals is through policy integration: Restructuring government departments away from siloed structures by enhancing communication processes and creating more cohesive administrative cultures with collective learning and increased common understandings, framings and methodologies. Several officials identify shared learning and understanding as a very important commitment that enables or counteracts the obstacles of siloed logic (Interview 1,3). There is a need for a systematic catalog of inclusive working methods, so that knowledge creation and collaboration always become inclusive (Interview 3). There is a need for structural changes rather than individual point efforts (interview 4). The Environmental Department's development work is largely based on externally financed projects. Such projects do not create continuity or structural change; rather they treat issues as isolated problems and at the end left for the next project. The evaluation processes and the possibility to incorporate successful projects into ordinary work are critical for implementing structural and long-lasting changes. With that said, it needs to be pointed out that working away from siloed structures does not mean removing separate departments altogether. But rather, it means creating an awareness of the issues of organization, framing, and inclusive knowledge production; further developing collaboration between departments; and promoting climate objectives and questions of (in)equity within other departments.

It should be noted that these propositions are based on data gathered that represents the interviewees' perceptions of their departments. The interview questions, and following the respondents' answers, are on a general level, as climate work is a huge and complex process. Therefore, for more precise, targeted suggestions, greater in-depth field-based work is necessary beyond the scope of this thesis. An interesting next step for future research could be to do

targeted examinations of different sectoral departments for a comparative study of how different institutional cultures affect the inclusion of climate-relevant social factors or a comparative study of different municipalities. Even though this research is case-specific, it might give insights that are useful when examining other institutions in Sweden and beyond.

7. Conclusion

In this Master's thesis, I have presented data and analysis drawn from a document analysis and interviews with government officials from Malmö Municipality. With this work, I hope I have made a convincing case for the use of qualitative mixed methods for intersectional policy analysis. I propose that an intersectional policy analysis needs to pay attention to 3 things: the context (the institutions and the history of the location), the social location of knowers (the historical trajectory of the institutions), and finally, the process of knowledge production. Therefore, I suggest that intersectional policy analysis requires not only to look at policy alone but also at the institution in which it exists, the key documents surrounding the issue, and how involved officials view the issue at hand. Secondly, I hope that I have made a convincing case for the need for a more inclusive and holistic view of climate issues and their connection to social factors. An intersectional analysis can help shift from single-axis thinking, where nature and society are seen as dualistic, to a perspective that sees them as interconnected. By analyzing documents and interviews, I found that the way Malmö municipality views and manages questions of (in)equity in their climate work is affected by the path-dependency of the institutions. Even if individual government officials are trying to create change, this historical trajectory falsely puts humans separate from nature, de-prioritizing certain types of issues and knowledges. Shifting to a more holistic perspective may highlight how societal power structures are intertwined with climate issues rather than being separate from them and how missing such an understanding will perpetuate societal injustice in climate policy and goals.

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9. Appendix

9.1. Interview invite

Slight variances of this invite were used depending on the situation and respondent contacted

Hello [name]!

My name is Angelica Lundgren. I am a Master student at the University of Gothenburg and am writing my master's thesis in the FORMAS-funded research project 'Climate policy and intersectionality'.

The project looks at how climate policy can become more socially inclusive. Our research is interested in how awareness of social differences, justice and equality issues in relation to climate policy can increase among Swedish decision-makers. In the first part of the research project, decision-making was examined at national level. In the second part of the study, we work with the municipalities' climate work. My thesis focuses on Malmö. The study will be based on a series of interviews with, among others, officials and politicians.

[How I got referred to the person and why]. Therefore, with this email I would like to invite you to an interview. It will take up to an hour and be done via Zoom. Would you be able to book such a meeting?

Looking forward to hearing from you!

Sincerely,

Angelica Lundgren

University of Gothenburg

Department of Global Studies

9.2. Interview guide

Thank you once again for taking the time for this meeting. This interview will take somewhere between 30 minutes to one hour. If it is okay with you I would like to record the sound, so I can later transcribe it. All information will be anonymized using a numbering system, e.g. Interview 1.

Background and role

To begin with, could you please tell me a little more about yourself and your role in the city of Malmö and in relation to the climate work in Malmö.

- Name:
- Role:
- Department:
- Which regulatory documents are central for your work?

Malmö municipality's work with sustainable development

In order to better grasp and understand your work with sustainable development, it is important to gain an understanding of the context in which different departments work, which is the purpose of the following questions; to get a better overall picture.

- How high on the agenda is the environmental and climate work within the city of Malmö?
- Are there any obstacles to taking climate action? And can you see that some types of action take precedence over others?

Sustainable development and justice

Climate change is unequal in its effects and different groups in society contribute differently to climate emissions. The City of Malmö strives to take measures for climate change that do not

create or deepen injustices, which is mentioned in e.g. the Climate Program. I am interested in whether and how you as a public employee work with this task and how you view these issues.

- Can you tell us a little about how the city of Malmö views fair climate policy and how your department handles justice issues in climate work?
- Do you think it can be done differently, in your eyes, and if so, how?
- Do you have any examples of [the department's] work concerning social differences and inequalities in society?
- Economic differences are primarily addressed as an obstacle to creating a fair sustainable development. Are there other social differences that may play a role?

Cooperation

Malmö municipality's regulatory documents highlight cooperation (samverkan) to be a key term in the city's climate work. That is what this next set of questions touch upon.

- Who does your department cooperate most closely with on environmental and climate issues? Both internally in the municipality and externally?
- How does the collaboration work in practice?

The first step in my research was a document analysis of the municipality's regulatory documents. Something that emerged then was that the documents do not differentiate between different groups in society. For example, in such a way that it means that EVERYONE must be involved.

- Is this interpretation correct? What has changed?
- How do you work with different groups in society?
- What do you think about citizens who are not organized?

Knowledge and information

- What type of information / knowledge do you use in your work?

- When you work on a sustainability or climate-related issue, where and from whom do you obtain what type of information in different parts of your work? Can you give examples?
- Do you think that showing types of knowledge can take up more space in the department than others?
- Can you come up with certain types of knowledge that do not take up as much space?

Possible follow-up question:

- Is there any other type of information and knowledge or special tools that you would need in your work on social justice and climate change?

Wrap-up

Thank you for your time, this was all the questions I had for you today.

- Do you think there is something we have missed? / Is there anything you would like to add?
- Do you have any questions for me?